

EFFECTS OF MAYOFASCIAL RELEASE WITH AND WITHOUT SUPPORT BELT FOR SACROILIAC JOINT PAIN AND ACTIVITY IN PREGNANT FEMALES

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Abstract

Background: The largest axial joints in the body, the sacroiliac joints (SIJs), are located on either side between the sacrum and pelvic bones. Most low back pain (LBP) is thought to originate in the lumbar spine; nonetheless, The SIJ is a potential additional cause of LBP that is frequently disregarded. In order to comprehend the anatomy, biomechanics, sexual dimorphism, and causes and mechanics of SIJ pain, this study (Parts I and II) intends to analyse the clinical and biomechanical literature. This evaluation will lead to choices for both conservative and surgical treatment employing instrumentation.

Objective: To determine the effects of myofascial release with and without support belt for sacroiliac joint pain and activity in pregnant females.

Methods: A randomized controlled trial was conducted involving postpartum individuals who underwent sacroiliac joint pain. Participants were randomly assigned to receive Myofascial release therapy with support belt, Myofascial release without support belt. Pain intensity and pelvic girdle, back pain disability were assessed using standardized scales at regular intervals

Results: A Significant difference was seen in score NPRS, PGQ, QBPDS Scale pre and post treatment with P-Value <0.05. The Mann-whitney and Willcoxon Test result showed no significant difference in all parameters. At same time, the independent t-test also showed no significant difference p-value <0.05.

Conclusion: The study concluded that for sacroiliac joint pain in pregnant female's myofascial release with support belt and myofascial release without support belt reduce pain but myofascial release with support belt is more effective treatment option to reduce pain and improve activity in patients.

INTRODUCTION

Sacroiliac joint discomfort is caused by pain in the SIJ's intra-articular tissues, including the articular

cartilage, interosseous ligaments, and anterior and posterior sacroiliac ligaments.(1) According to

studies, 13–30% of people experience sacroiliac joint pain. One in five women experience sacroiliac joint pain (SIJP) throughout pregnancy and the postpartum period, which causes some pelvic discomfort. Some of them have considerable discomfort, which could persist into the postpartum period.(2) Effective chronic illness prevention and pain control. One should take this seriously if they care about the welfare of women. Potential risk factors for sacroiliac joint dysfunction include gender, lower BMI, pregnancy-related changes to the pelvic blood circulation and muscle endurance, sacroiliac joint haemorrhage during childbirth, hormonally-induced joint laxity, and gender-related variations in the sacroiliac joint's biomechanical behaviours(3). This Fortin region test diagnosis is strongly linked to SIJD.(4) The SIJD is typically acknowledged as the main factor contributing to low back pain. Women experience it more frequently.(5) Sacroiliac joint dysfunction is hypothesized to affect women more frequently than men because of the load-bearing surfaces in the SI joint, the effects of pregnancy, leading a sedentary lifestyle, or standing for long periods of time with the sacrum more horizontal(6). Gender, lower BMI, pregnancy-induced changes to the pelvic blood circulation and muscle endurance, sacroiliac joint hemorrhage during childbirth, hormonally-induced joint laxity, and gender-related variations in the sacroiliac joint's biomechanical behaviors are all potential risk factors for sacroiliac joint dysfunction. This Fortin region test diagnosis is strongly linked to SIJD. (7)Due to high prevalence of sacroiliac joint pain during pregnancy worldwide and its associated problems have raised concerns among the women health physiotherapist to carefully manage the females during pregnancy period to improve their sacroiliac joint pain and activity(8). The results of this study can assist physiotherapists in treating sacroiliac joint discomfort in pregnant women with myofascial release, either with or without the use of a support belt(9).

The present investigation focuses on two distinct approaches to treating sacroiliac joint discomfort. Myofascial release with a support belt is the first technique, while myofascial release without a support belt is the second. Baseline treatment included muscle stabilizing exercises, heating packs and (TENS). Group A consists of seventeen patients who

get up to 600 seconds of myofascial release therapy in the sacroiliac joint region (10). The active release technique, which involves applying steady pressure with the thumb for 60 seconds at a time while repeating the procedure ten times at each trigger point, was used to perform myofascial release on the sacroiliac region. The participant's tolerance determined the pressure intensity. The restrictive tissue barrier was then subjected to constant, prolonged pressure to loosen the fascia. The total treatment sessions was 12 in 4 weeks, a support belt should only be worn for two to three hours at a time, and it was used four times a week for three sessions each week.(11)

Group B consists of seventeen patients who get up to 600 seconds of myofascial release therapy in the sacroiliac joint region. The active release technique, which involves applying steady pressure with the thumb for 60 seconds at a time while repeating the procedure ten times at each trigger point, was used to perform myofascial release on the sacroiliac region. The participant's tolerance determined the pressure intensity. The restrictive tissue barrier was then subjected to constant, prolonged pressure to loosen the fascia. Twelve therapy sessions were completed in four weeks, although no support belt was used. Data were gathered and examined at baseline and during the 4-week follow-up.(12)

Due to high prevalence of sacroiliac joint pain during pregnancy worldwide and its associated problems have raised concerns among the women health physiotherapist to carefully manage the females during pregnancy period to improve their sacroiliac joint pain and activity. The results of this study can assist physiotherapists in treating sacroiliac joint discomfort in pregnant women with myofascial release, either with or without the use of a support belt.

Rationale:

Complications during pregnancy, such as sacroiliac joint pain, contribute to maternal health risks. Effective non-pharmacological interventions are vital for improving maternal outcomes. In regions with limited healthcare access like rural Pakistan, pregnant women may lack specialized care for musculoskeletal pain. Exploring accessible options like myofascial release therapy could address this gap.

Sacroiliac joint pain can hinder pregnant women's daily activities, impacting family dynamics and socioeconomic well-being. Optimizing healthcare resources is crucial in resource-constrained settings. If myofascial release therapy proves effective in reducing sacroiliac joint pain and improving activity levels in pregnant females and sustainable intervention option for healthcare providers to incorporate into prenatal care protocols.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study Design: This study was randomized controlled trial. **Study Setting:** This study was conducted in the Shaikh Zayed Hospital Lahore. **Duration:** The data was collected from January 20, 2023 to July 3, 2023 after approval of synopsis. **Sample Size:** thirty four sample size was calculated by using mean difference between the groups according to numeric pain rating scale. Confidence Interval is (2-sided) 95%. Power is 80%. Ratio of sample size (Group 2/Group 1) was (3.3±2.4 vs. 5.9±2.8) calculated from Open Epi, Version 3, By adding 10% attrition rate, (13). **Study groups: Group A:** Myofascial release with a support belt. **Group B(12):** Myofascial release without support belt. Baseline treatment included muscle stabilizing exercises, heating packs and (TENS)(14, 15). **Sampling Technique:** Simple Randomly allocated into groups through Lottery Method. by placing name chits in a bowl and randomly picking one by one and allocating 17 individuals in each group.

Sample Selection:

Inclusion Criteria: 20-40 years of age. The second and third trimesters of pregnancy (16). In order to diagnosis SIJ pain, relies on bilateral posterior inferior iliac spine sensitivity, significant pain was detected by the Patrick's Faber test, Gaenslen's test, the compression test, and the posterior pelvic pain provocation/thigh thrust test. The existence of SIJ discomfort was indicated by positive responses from at least three of those provocative tests. **Exclusion Criteria:** A history of rheumatoid arthritis. A herniated disc in the lumbar spine or a back injury. A prior lumbar spine operation. Pregnancy at high risk. Any systemic illness of the bones or soft tissues. Malignancy(17).

Data Collection Procedure: All study participants were made aware of the goal and methodology prior to the trial. Each of them signed the appropriate informed permission form before proceeding with the study and processing their personal data for research purposes.(18) This is to certify that all research was carried out in compliance with the necessary policies and laws. Tenderness was confined to the posterior inferior iliac spine on both sides for the diagnosis of SIJ discomfort. Provocative maneuvers of the SIJT high thrust test, provocative maneuvers of the SIJ, The compression test, The Gaenslen's test, and The Patrick's Faber test all produced severe discomfort. The existence of SIJ discomfort was indicated by positive responses from at least three of that provocative test. How you measure the entire test.

Numeric Pain Rating Scale: Numeric pain rating scale compromises a 0-10 number, 0 indicates no pain while 10 indicates worse pain. Patients were asked to pick a number to rate their pain. It was a highly acceptable scale¹². After obtaining all the data we proceeded towards statistical analysis.

The Quebec scale for functional disability scoring spans from 0 to 5, with anchor points denoting "no difficulty" at zero and "unable to do" at five. This scale produces a subjective disability score ranging from 0 to 100, where elevated scores signify more pronounced impairment.

The Pelvic Girdle Pain Questionnaire (PGQ) is a specialized tool designed to evaluate activity limitations (PGQ Activity, consisting of 20 items) and symptoms (PGQ Symptom, consisting of 5 items) in women experiencing PGP during pregnancy and postpartum. Each of the 20 items in the PGQ Activity section and 5 items in the PGQ Symptom section is rated on a 4-point descriptive scale ranging from 0 to 3. The total PGQ score is calculated by summing all individual item scores and then dividing by the total possible score of 75 (comprising a maximum of 60 for activity and 15 for symptoms). This score is then converted into a percentage, resulting in a range from 0 (indicating no disability) to 100 (indicating severe disability), using the formula: Maximum Score 75 % Disability = (total score/75) x 100.

Stuge B, Garratt A, Jenssen H, Grotle M. The Pelvic Girdle Questionnaire: A ConditionSpecific

Instrument for Assessing Activity Limitations and Symptoms in People with Pelvic Girdle Pain. *Physical Therapy*. July 2011; 91(7): 1096-1108.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

Data was entered and analyzed using computer software SPSS version 26. The quantitative variables of the study was presented as mean ± s.d whereas qualitative data was presented in the form of Frequency (Percentage). Shapiro-Wilk test was used for normality of the data as Shapiro-Wilk test is greater than 0.0 so we applied parametric test. The chi-square test was utilized to ascertain disparities between groups concerning outcomes, while an independent sample t-test was employed for quantitative variables. Paired t-test analysis was conducted to evaluate the mean difference between pre- and post-outcome measures, including PGQ, Quebec scale, and NPRS. For non-parametric test across and Within-group analysis for the pre- and post-treatment values of both groups using the Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test, the Mann-Whitney U Test, the Paired Sample T Test, and the Independent Sample T Test for the variables NPRS, PGQTS, and QBPDS. A p-value of ≤ 0.05 was deemed statistically significant.

RESULTS

After screening 40 patients, 34 participants who fulfilled the inclusion criteria were included in the study. Participants were randomly allocated into two groups using the lottery method. Two dropouts from Group B and one from Group A were reported. Figure 1 displays the flow diagram for CONSORT. There were 16 participants in group A and 15 in group B, the minimum age of patients in both groups is 20.00 and maximum age 38.00 and mean age was 28.77 ± 5.05 years. For four weeks, each participant had three sessions each week on different days. Version 25 of SPSS was used to analyse the data.

In Table 1, demographic characteristics are displayed. Tables 2 and 3 present the results of the Across and Within-group analysis for the pre- and post-treatment values of both groups using the Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test, the Mann-Whitney U Test, the Paired Sample T Test, and the Independent Sample T Test for the variables NPRS, PGQTS, and QBPDS.

A Significant difference was seen in score NPRS, PGQ, QBPDS Scale pre and post treatment with P-Value <0.05. The Mann-Whitney and Wilcoxon Test result showed no significant difference in all parameters. At same time, the independent t-test also showed no significant difference p-value <0.05.

So, Sacroiliac joint pain in pregnant female’s myofascial release with support belt and myofascial release without support belt reduce pain but myofascial release with support belt is more effective treatment option to reduce pain and improve activity in patients.

DISCUSSION:

The current study aimed to examine the benefits of myofascial release for sacroiliac joint activity and discomfort during pregnancy with and without a support belt. The results of the current study demonstrated a significant improvement in the numeric pain rating scale, pelvic girdle questionnaire, and Quebec back pain disability scale post intervention in the myofascial release group with and without support belt as compared to the pre-intervention values. However, there is a more significant improvement in the NPRS, PGQ, and QBPDS of post intervention values as compared to the pre-intervention values in the myofascial release group with and without support belt despite the fact that both treatment approaches were successful. The myofascial release with support belt is a better treatment technique as compared to the myofascial release without support belt.

In a 2015(19) randomised clinical trial research, the effectiveness of the medication was evaluated at 4 and 12 weeks. The 51 patients' side symptoms were successfully managed. 4 out of 15 patients responded well to physiotherapy, 14 out of 18 responded well to manual therapy, and 7 out of 18 patients (or 50%) responded well to intra-articular injections (p = 0.01). Compared to physiotherapy and other therapies, manual treatment had better results. In present study there is significant results for SIJ pain. In NPRS for both groups myofascial release with support belt and myofascial release without support belt p-value is .000 but myofascial release with support belt have more significant results. PGQTS Post-Treatment for myofascial release with support belt p-value is .000 and myofascial release without support belt p-value

is .002, so myofascial release with support belt is better treatment option. Quebec Back Pain Disability Scale Post-Treatment (QBPDS) for myofascial release with support belt and without support belt both are effective treatment but myofascial release with support belt have more significant difference and it is better treatment option. This study was contrast to present study because of the different types of treatments.

Author JE Horasanlı 2021(20) shows that effectiveness of kinesiotaping for sacroiliac joint discomfort in pregnant patients. Result Age, parity, gravidas, gestational week, and body mass index were comparable across the KT and fake KT groups. There were no statistically significant differences in the VAS, RMDQ, or PGQ scores between the two groups at the beginning of the investigation. After five weeks, the VAS, RMDQ, and PGQ scores of the sham KT group had not significantly improved, but the KT group had demonstrated significant overall improvements. After undergoing KT treatment, pregnant women who experienced sacroiliac joint discomfort noticed improvements in their pain levels, functional abilities, and quality of life. This study examined the effects of myofascial release on sacroiliac joint discomfort and activity in pregnant women with and without support belts. Results In terms of age, parity, gravidas, trimester, and body mass index, and two groups were comparable. There is statistically difference in NPRS, PGQ and QBPDS (21)of both groups but more difference in the myofascial release with support belt because p- value is less than 0.05 This study was contrast to present study because of the different types of treatments but in both studies there is usage of PGQ.

In 2018 author J Bertuit shows that SIJ pain during pregnancy mostly triggered between the 14th and 21st week of pregnancy and pelvic discomfort began. The pain threshold was 60 ± 20 mm. Daily activities could make pain worse. Belt usage lessened discomfort. On a visual analogue scale, there was a 20 mm reduction in pain intensity. Additionally, everyday tasks were simplified. All of these results, however, are only true if pregnant women wore belts often for brief periods of time. In the present study 2nd and 3rd trimester pregnant females was included and the pain P- value before treatment was .140 and after treatment there was p-value was .000 there is

significant difference in reduction of pain after usage of pelvic belt with myofascial release This literature is not contrast the present study because in both studies there is usage of supports belts and studies have similar effects(22)

CONCLUSION:

The study concluded that for sacroiliac joint pain in pregnant female's myofascial release with support belt and myofascial release without support belt reduce pain but myofascial release with support belt is more effective treatment option to reduce pain and improve activity in patients.

Limitation of study

- Patient's daily routine schedule was not recorded which may have their pelvic pain during the treatment interval.
- Patients had fear of movement while diagnosis of SIJ pain.
- Lack of long term follow up due to short duration study.

Recommendations

- It is recommended that Myofascial release should be compared with other physiotherapy treatment techniques for pregnant females of sacroiliac joint pain.
- Physiotherapist should give awareness to the pregnant females about support belts. Throughout all three trimesters, using a maternity support belt enhanced balance and decreased the chance of falling.
- By taking some of the weight off the belly and stabilizing the body, supports belts may help to ease some of the aches and pains that might develop during pregnancy.
- Future research can also be done to see the effect of minimum session of myofascial release with support belt with the combination of other therapy required to treat the pregnant females with SIJ pain.
- Physiotherapist should also give awareness to the people about the efficiency of myofascial release, supports belts or maternity belts and also other physiotherapy treatment during pregnancy for the SIJ pain.
- Abbreviations

- DBM: Dannis Bois Method; MFR: Myofascial Release; FM: Fascial Manipulation; NPRS: Numeric Pain Rating Scale; NDI: Neck Disability Index; CONSORT: Consolidated Standards of Reporting Trials.

Declarations

Ethics approval and consent to participate

The study protocol was approved by the Institutional Review Committee of Riphah International University Islamabad (Lahore Campus), Pakistan with reference no.F21C14G92006 REC/RCRS/22/0102 and followed as per guidelines. All the participants provided written informed consent to participate in the study. The method use in this study was according to CONSORT guidelines. **All methods were carried out in accordance with relevant guidelines and regulations.**

Consent for publication

Not applicable.

Availability of Data

Data will be available at a reasonable request from the corresponding author.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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Authors' contributions

DR Maria Shabbir & Ghulam Fatima Contributing In Study Design, DATA COLLECTION, Statistical Analysis, DR Mariya Tariq Contributing In DATA COLLECTION & Manuscript Preparation, DR Khalid Abbas & Shafaq Naeem helping us in DATA COLLECTION. Miss Madiha Iqbal Statistical Analysis, Manuscript Preparation.

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Table 1: Baseline Demographics of Both Groups

Baseline characters	Myofascial release with support belt group (A)	Myofascial release without support belt group (B)
No. of participants	16	15
Gender	Females	Females
Mean age	28.77 ± 5.05	28.77 ± 5.05

Table 2: Across and within-group comparison of NPRS, PGQTS Mann-Whitney U Test. Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test.

	Group A Mean Rank	Group B Mean Rank	Median	P-value
Pre-NPRS	18.25	13.600	8-6	0.14
Post-NPRS	9.75	22.60	1-5	0.00
Median	8-1	6-5		
P-value	0.14	0.00		
	Group A Mean Rank	Group B Mean Rank	Median	P-value
Pre-PGQTS	18.56	13.27	61-45	0.10
Post-PGQTS	9.00	23.47	5.9-36.6	0.00
Median	61-5.9	45-36.6		
P-value	0.10	0.00		

[Abbreviations:NPRS=Numeric Pain Rating Scale; PGQTS=Pelvic Girdle Questionnaire].

Table 3: Across and Within-group comparison of Quebec Scale for Functional Disability Total Score.

	Group A (Mean±S.D)	Group B (Mean±S.D)	Mean Difference	P-value
Quebec Scale for Functional Disability Total Score Pre-Treatment	50.8±13.40	42.8±14.73	8.0	0.121
Quebec Scale for Functional Disability Total Score Post-Treatment	6.93±6.00	32.93±15.13	-25.99	0.02
Mean Difference	8.07	-25.99		
P-value	0.121	0.01		
	Group A (Mean±S.D)	Group B (Mean±S.D)	Mean Difference	P-value
Quebec Scale for Functional Disability Total Score Pre-Treatment	50.87 ± 13.40	6.93 ± 6.00	14.65	0.00
Quebec Scale for Functional Disability Total Score Post-Treatment	42.80 ± 14.73	32.93 ± 15.13	4.81	0.00
Mean Difference	14.65	4.81		
P-value	0.00	0.00		

[Abbreviations:Quebec Scale for Functional Disability Total Score].

Figure: CONSORT Diagram